

Chemical Examination of the Leaves, Stem Bark and Root Bark of *Morinda tinctoria* Var. *Tomentosa**

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The leaves of *M. tinctoria* var. *tomentosa* yielded ursolic acid while its stem bark gave alizarin-1-methyl ether, rubiadin and D-mannitol. Anthragallol-2,3-dimethyl ether, soranjidiol and ibericin were obtained from the root bark besides the glycoside 6-primeveroside of morindone.

MORINDA tinctoria var. *tomentosa* (family: Rubiaceae) is a wild species commonly found in the Telangana forests of Andhra Pradesh. The root bark of this plant was earlier examined by Rao and Veera Reddy¹ who isolated and characterised the glycoside of morindone as the 6-primeveroside of morindone. The present investigation deals with the isolation and characterisation of the various chemical constituents of the leaves, stem bark and the root bark of the same plant.

Examination of leaves :

Dried and powdered leaves (1.0 kg) were extracted with light pet. ether (60-80), ether, acetone and ethanol in succession in a soxhlet apparatus. The gummy dark green solid (11.0 g) obtained on evaporation of the pet. ether extract was saponified and the unsaponifiable material crystallised from ethyl acetate as colourless needles (2.5 g), identified as ursolic acid, $C_{30}H_{48}O_8$, m.p. 284°, $(\alpha)_D^{25} + 72.4^\circ$ (c. 0.35 in MeOH); acetate, $C_{32}H_{50}O_4$, m.p. 286°, $(\alpha)_D^{25} + 62.5^\circ$ (c. 1.0 in $CHCl_3$); monomethyl ester, $C_{31}H_{50}O_3$ (ethereal CH_2N_2), crystallised from methanol as colourless needles, m.p. 169-70°, $(\alpha)_D^{25} + 62.7^\circ$ (c. 1.0 in $CHCl_3$). The ether extract of the leaves gave some more (1.5 g) ursolic acid while the acetone and the ethanol extracts on usual work up gave gummy intractable materials.

Examination of stem bark :

Dried, powdered stem bark (1.0 kg) was extracted with pet. ether and ethanol. The gummy solid (2.5 g), obtained on evaporation of the pet. ether extract was chromatographed on a column of sigel. Pet. ether and pet. ether-benzene (1 : 1) eluted wax (1.0 g). Benzene eluted a yellow crystalline compound (0.5 g) which separated as yellow needles from acetic acid, $C_{18}H_{10}O_4$, m.p. 182-4°. The uv and ir data suggested that the compound to be alizarin-1-methyl ether².

The benzene-chloroform (2 : 1) eluate gave a yellow compound (0.3 g) which separated as yellow needles from benzene, $C_{15}H_{10}O_4$, m.p. 302°. Its

uv and ir data suggested that it may be rubiadin³; acetate, m.p. 228°. Subsequent extraction of the stem bark with ethanol was followed by fractionation of the concentrated ethanol extract with ether, ethyl acetate and *n*-butanol in succession. The ether fraction did not yield any crystalline product while the ethyl acetate fraction gave a gummy hygroscopic solid answering tests for anthraquinones and glycosides. Further work on this mixture was not possible owing to paucity of material. The *n*-butanol extract on concentration and cooling gave D-mannitol (1.0 g), $C_6H_{14}O_6$, m.p. 166°, $(\alpha)_D^{25} - 2.1^\circ$ (water).

Examination of the root bark :

Fresh fleshy root bark (1.0 kg) was pulverised with ethanol in a blender. Evaporation of the extract gave a syrup which was fractionated with ether and chloroform-methanol (3 : 1). The ether extractable portion (2.4 g) was chromatographed on a column of sigel. Pet. ether-benzene (1 : 1) eluted colourless wax. Benzene eluted an orange compound (0.26 g) crystallising as needles from glacial acetic acid, $C_{16}H_{12}O_5$, m.p. 166-8°. Colour reactions and spectral data suggested that the compound was anthragallol-2,3-dimethyl ether⁴.

Benzene-chloroform (2 : 1) eluted an orange yellow solid (0.1 g) which crystallised from benzene as needles, $C_{15}H_{10}O_4$, m.p. 275°, identified as soranjidiol⁵.

Chloroform eluate gave a pale yellow compound (Ia) (0.35 g) crystallising from glacial acetic acid as needles, $C_{17}H_{14}O_5$, m.p. 182°. Its acetate (Ac_2O -Py; reflux, 2 hr) (Ib), crystallised from ethanol as pale yellow needles, $C_{21}H_{18}O_7$, m.p. 163°. PMR ($CDCl_3$): δ 1.1 (t, 3H, methyl), 2.32 (s, 3H, methyl of 3-acetyl), 2.45 (s, 3H, methyl of 1-acetyl), 3.4 (q, 2H, methylenic), 4.5 (s, 2H, benzylic CH_2), 8.0 (m, 5H, aromatic). These data suggested that the compound was ibericin (Ia) i.e., the β -ethyl ether of lucidin. Ibericin was considered to be an artefact^{6,7}, arising from lucidin during the

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course of extraction of the plant material with ethanol. The highly reactive benzylic alcoholic group of lucidin reacts with ethanol to give ibericin. It may be that the compound may be an artefact in the present investigation also.

Ia, R-H; Ib, R-COCH₃

The chloroform-methanol (3 : 1) extract on usual workup gave an orange yellow compound crystallising from 66% ethanol as yellow needles, m.p. 244-46°, (α)_D²⁵-84.6° (c, 0.54 in dioxane). It was identified as the 6-primeveroside of morindone by direct comparison with an authentic sample¹.

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